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Mediatization as a Fundamental Communication Strategy of University Libraries in Kharkiv

Objective. The aim of the study is to develop conceptual foundations for mediatization as the most effective communication strategy for university libraries. The unique experience of analytical and marketing practices in scientific libraries of universities enables them to effectively monitor the impact of their official accounts on social networks and messaging platforms, thereby contributing to the formation of their unique image. **Methods.** Employed methods include observation, comparison, Internet marketing, content analysis of official university websites, references to official web representations on social networks (messengers), statistical and mathematical methods, as well as systemic and socio-communicative approaches. **Results.** The study clarified the extent of Kharkiv universities' incorporation into the global communication space through their web presence activity on various social networks/messengers. Rankings for the popularity of social networks/messengers (Facebook, YouTube, Instagram, Telegram) among Kharkiv universities, as well as for their Telegram channels based on the number of subscribers were developed. **Conclusions.** University libraries possess powerful analytical potential for enhancing the effectiveness of universities' branding campaigns through mediatization – effective communication activities on social networks/messengers. Systematic use of web analytics tools to monitor the effectiveness of communication strategies and adapt content according to subscribers' interests can improve the quality of communication and marketing activities in higher education institutions.

Keywords: university libraries in Kharkiv; mediatization; social networks; messengers; Internet marketing; branding

Introduction

Contemporary society is increasingly orienting towards digital communication, accelerating the mediatization process – the essence of which involves social networks and messengers becoming the primary means of communication and interaction for millions of people worldwide. Digital media are now the fundamental communication intermediary between society and the higher education system. They have a decisive impact on potential applicants' perceptions of the status of a higher education institution (HEI) and the quality of its educational services. In the highly competitive environment of educational services, the effectiveness of modern HEIs' branding depends on their active use of social networks/messengers as a fundamental tool for communicating with prospective and current students, alumni, and other stakeholders to shape the institution's unique image and its promotion within the global educational space.

Higher education institutions in Ukraine are facing competitive challenges to attract prospective students both domestically and from abroad. In the context of Russia's full-scale

invasion to Ukraine, foreign universities are offering Ukrainian applicants simplified and advantageous admission conditions. Kharkiv, known as the student capital of Ukraine, has lost its status because of its location in a conflict zone. As a result, Kharkiv universities need to intensify their use of various digital media as communication channels to effectively position themselves in the global communication space and attract a greater number of potential students. University libraries, as the most qualified communication entities in the global digital media space, expertly perform system analytical and marketing functions, systematically monitor universities' official web representations, enhancing the effectiveness of shaping and promoting HEI's attractive image. Libraries most effectively monitor the capabilities, capacities and popularity of digital media to ensure that the content posted and promoted by HEIs achieves maximum impact and feedback.

Kharkiv higher education institutions are increasingly seeking new resources and communication channels to develop effective branding strategies and enhance their corporate image. Theoretical principles for solving this issue have been explored in the works of M. Camilleri (2019), V. Baltezarevic (2023), Lai-Wan Wong and co-authors (2022), N. Tkachova, O. Shevtsova (2020), A. Baranetska (2020), V. Berezenko and co-authors (2021) and others. M. Camilleri (2019), in his article "Higher Education Marketing: Opportunities and Challenges in the Digital Era", conducts critical audit of the marketing environment in higher education institutions using SWOT analysis for the assessment of internal and external factors that may influence the development of an effective image and the implementation of services oriented toward modern higher education students. According to V. Baltezarevic (2023), the author of "The Role of Digital Marketing in the Education Sector", among many digital marketing activities, optimizing websites for search engines, content marketing on social networks, and engagement of influencers have proven to be the most effective for users in the sector of higher education. Lai-Wan Wong and co-authors (2022), in their article "Mobile Social Media Marketing: A New Marketing Channel among Digital Natives in Higher Education", study the specifics of mobile marketing in social media, considering the fact that contemporary youth are a digital generation. The authors demonstrate the effectiveness of mobile technologies and their ease of use, as well as their strong social impact for attracting prospective students to HEIs. Researchers N. Tkachova and O. Shevtsova (2020), in their article "Social Media as an Effective Method of Promoting Educational Services in Times of Crisis", provide a list of measures for effective promotion of HEIs on the Internet, including website popularization, utilizing YouTube features, email marketing, online surveys among high school students and their parents, etc.

Other scientific research, such as A. Baranetska (2020) in her article "Integrated Communications: Interpretation of Advertising", V. Berezenko and co-authors (2021) in "Advertising in the Conditions of Digitalization: Ukrainian Realities", Shelestova A., Solianyuk A., Bachynska N., Novalska T., Kobieliiev O. (2021) in "Libraries of Pedagogical Institutions of Higher Education on Social Media", and Davydova I., Marina O., Solianyuk A., Syerov Y. (2019) in "Social Networks in Developing the Internet Strategy for Libraries in Ukraine", fragmentarily consider tools for enhancing the effectiveness of digital advertising on social networks. Nevertheless, current publications lack a comprehensive branding strategy for HEIs with a thorough list of digital web analytics tools which modern university libraries professionally utilize.

The objective of this research is to develop conceptual foundations for medialization as the most effective communication strategy in university libraries.

Methods

The research was conducted based on a content analysis of official university websites, calls to official university web representatives on social networks (messengers), and each web representation was subsequently examined for relevance and number of subscribers. The following methods were employed to carry out the study: searching for official HEIs websites and identifying their official web representations on social networks/messengers; analyzing the official web representations of universities on social networks/messengers (such as Facebook, YouTube, Instagram, Telegram, X (formerly Twitter), LinkedIn, etc.) by libraries; collecting and analyzing data on the number of subscribers for each official web presence of universities on each social network/messenger; applying statistical and mathematical methods for creating rankings of social networks/messengers and identifying platforms, popular among universities. Using diagram construction method allowed to visualize and organize the collected statistical data. Methodological tools for systemic and socio-communicative approaches facilitated the development of an effective branding communication strategy for HEIs based on the activation of the medialization process by university libraries.

Results and Discussion

To investigate the state of HEIs' integration into the modern web space, the official web presences of 20 Kharkiv state-owned HEIs of III-IV accreditation levels were analyzed. These institutions have websites and web representations on social networks and messengers. Table 1 provides links to the official web presences on social networks and messengers collected from the HEIs' official websites.

According to the data presented in Table 1, all Kharkiv HEIs have official web representations on the Internet, registered on various platforms. However, most institutions are present on the most popular platforms, which is understandable given that, in the context of branding, promotion is more advantageous where the audience is larger.

Table 1

Official web representations of institutions of higher education of the III-IV levels of accreditation of the state-owned form of Kharkiv¹

Name of the institution of higher education	Website URL	Link to the official Facebook page	Link to the official Instagram page	Link to the official YouTube page	Link to the official Telegram page	Other social networks
State Biotechnological University	https://biotechuniv.edu.ua/	https://www.facebook.com/dbtu.official	https://www.instagram.com/dbtu_official/	https://youtube.com/@biotechuniv?feature=shared	—	—
National Aerospace University «Kharkiv Aviation Institute»	https://khai.edu.ua/	https://www.facebook.com/aerospaceuniversity	https://www.instagram.com/aerospaceuniversity/	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCCEZWQqN-7IO1t343VCT1oQ	https://t.me/aerospaceuniversity	—

¹ The data were collected by the authors as of June 30, 2024

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National Technical University «Kharkiv Polytechnic Institute»	http://www.kpi.kharkov.ua	http://www.facebook.com/ntu.xpi	https://www.instagram.com/ntu.khpi	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCnkp4oOPGFmq5em2dtTPH-w	https://t.me/s/NTU_KhPI_press	https://twitter.com/ntu_xpi https://www.linkedin.com/edu/school?id=192052 https://vimeo.com/presskhi
National University of Civil Defence of Ukraine	http://www.nuczu.edu.ua	https://www.facebook.com/nuczu.edu.ua/	https://www.instagram.com/nuczu_ukraine/	https://www.youtube.com/user/nuczu	https://t.me/nuczu_vstup	https://twitter.com/nuczukr
National University of Pharmacy	http://nuph.edu.ua	https://www.facebook.com/nuph.edu.ua	https://www.instagram.com/nuph.edu.ua/	https://www.youtube.com/c/nuph_officially	—	https://www.tiktok.com/@nuph.edu.ua
Yaroslav Mudryi National Law University	http://nlu.edu.ua/	https://www.facebook.com/nlu.official	https://www.instagram.com/nlu_official	https://www.youtube.com/NulauOrgUA	https://t.me/NLU1804official	https://twitter.com/nlu_edu_ua https://www.linkedin.com/edu/school?id=372095
Ukrainian Engineering and Pedagogical Academy	http://www.uipa.edu.ua	https://www.facebook.com/uepa.official/	https://www.instagram.com/uepa.official/	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCarHROiYw40r876rXXelbKA/featured	https://t.me/uepakhar_kiv	—
Ukrainian state university of railway transport	http://kart.edu.ua	https://www.facebook.com/ukrdzt.University/	https://instagram.com/ukrdzt_university?igshid=zducgcauc818	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UC-xwIAvnnd1Gzm0KY5Dgmrw	https://t.me/UkrDuzt_of	—
Kharkiv State Academy of Design and fine Arts	http://www.ksada.org	https://www.facebook.com/profile.php?id=100076092646516	https://www.instagram.com/ksada.kharkiv/	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCno7QcurcFI_IXRsRkEclnQ	—	—
Kharkiv State Academy of Culture	http://www.ic.ac.kharkov.ua	https://www.facebook.com/ksac.kharkiv?locale=uk_UA	https://www.instagram.com/ksac.kharkiv/	https://www.youtube.com/@user-po3dc9rq5w	https://t.me/hdakvstup2023	—
Kharkiv State Academy of Physical Culture	https://khdafk.com.ua	https://www.facebook.com/HGAFK	https://www.instagram.com/_khdafk/	https://www.youtube.com/c/HDAFK	—	—

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Kharkiv National Automobile and Highway University	http://www.khadi.kharkov.ua	https://www.facebook.com/khnahu/	https://www.instagram.com/khnaduuniversity/	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UC8MWxx9covI5HQcQrGQdMCA?view_as=subscriber	https://t.me/khnahu/	—
Simon Kuznets Kharkov National University of Economics	http://www.hneu.edu.ua	https://www.facebook.com/khneu	https://www.instagram.com/khneu/	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCxG7LPUimHBYu5BRyPiUr_g	https://t.me/abitura_2019	https://twitter.com/KHNEU https://www.linkedin.com/school/kharkiv-national-university-of-economics/ https://www.tiktok.com/@khneu
Kharkiv National Medical University	http://knmu.edu.ua	https://www.facebook.com/knmu.1804/	https://www.instagram.com/knmu.kharkiv/?igshid=YjNmNGQ3MDY%3D	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCAhDsjM3fEDwftz8oogRVDg/videos	https://t.me/KhNMUof978	https://www.linkedin.com/company/knmu-official https://twitter.com/knmu_official https://www.pinterest.com/knmu_official
Kharkiv National University of Internal Affairs	http://www.univdu.ua	https://www.facebook.com/khnuia/	https://www.instagram.com/khnuivs/	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCF9VDxyP3Eeq53otGATwGKQ	https://t.me/khnuia	https://x.com/khnuivs
V. N. Karazin Kharkiv National University	https://karazin.ua/	https://www.facebook.com/Karazin.University	https://www.instagram.com/karazinuniver	https://www.youtube.com/c/KarazinUniver	https://t.me/karazinuniver1804	https://www.tiktok.com/@karazinuniver
H.S. Skovoroda Kharkiv National Pedagogical University	http://hnpu.edu.ua	https://www.facebook.com/groups/1029347057130340/ https://www.facebook.com/KhNPU	http://www.instagram.com/sk.times/?utm_source=ig_profile_share&igshid=sq991sb25cc5	http://www.youtube.com/channel/UCDJGxeq1Vlbcn26Yy7Y2gQg?view_as=subscriber	https://web.telegram.org/#/im?p=@Skovoroda_university	—

Kharkiv National University of Arts named after I. P. Kotlyarevsky	http://num.kharkiv.ua	https://www.facebook.com/HNUM-Kotlyarevsky-101345511960603/	—	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCAGqv90SOPDvyvZMpcHxCog	—	—
O.M. Beketov National University of Urban Economy in Kharkiv	http://www.kname.edu.ua	https://www.facebook.com/Beketov1922/	https://www.instagram.com/beketovuni/	https://www.youtube.com/@BeketovUni	https://t.me/beketovuni_vstup	—
Kharkiv National University of Radio Electronics	http://nure.ua	https://www.facebook.com/nureKharkiv/	https://www.instagram.com/khnure_official/	https://www.youtube.com/user/nuretvtv	https://t.me/nure_osvita	https://www.linkedin.com/school/kharkiv-national-university-of-radioelectronics/ https://twitter.com/PressNURE

To maximize coverage of the target and potential audience, who may prefer different platforms, it is advisable for higher education institutions (HEIs) to maintain web presences on multiple platforms, each with its own specific characteristics. For example, most universities have official pages on Facebook, where they post news, information about events, activities, academic achievements of their students and faculties, and campus life, among other things. Importantly, Facebook allows HEIs to interact with their audience through comments, messages, and polls. This fosters the creation of an active community around the institution. Additionally, the platform is used to disseminate promotional content for prospective students.

Instagram is also an extremely popular social network, especially among young people. Most universities actively use Instagram for visual presentation of their life, as Instagram is more oriented towards photos and short videos, and allows for live streaming. Most HEIs interact with their audience through:

- publishing visual content, actively promoting advertising materials to attract prospective students;

- Stories allows sharing temporary updates that disappear after 24 hours, making it convenient for event announcements or showcasing daily life at the institution;

- IGTV and Reels: using longer videos on IGTV and short, dynamic videos on Reels helps create diverse and attractive content that can involve more followers and maintain their interest.

YouTube is a powerful tool for higher education institutions to communicate with their audience. Interaction occurs through the publication of video content in the following formats:

- educational content: recorded or live-streamed classes, lectures, and seminars; instructional videos explaining complex topics or demonstrating practical skills;

- informational and promotional content: institutional video introductions (educational programs); video announcements about important news, events, etc.; information for prospective students about admission conditions, deadlines, and program specifics in video format;

- promotion of events and content: promotional videos for upcoming events, conferences, open days; live streams or recordings of significant events such as graduation ceremonies, festive events, etc.;

- testimonials and success stories: videos featuring testimonials about studying and life at the institution; interviews and stories about alumni successes and their professional achievements;

- research content: video presentations of research and projects results, etc.; interviews with scholars, discussions with faculty and researchers about their work, relevant and successful research projects;

- support and consultancy: videos offering advice concerning studying, career choice, exam preparation; recorded webinars on various topics useful to higher education students;

- cultural and social events: videos of cultural events, concerts, exhibitions; videos about social initiatives, charity events, and volunteer projects;

- vlogs: videos from students about their daily life, studies, and leisure; videos from faculty about their teaching methods, projects, and research.

X (formerly Twitter) is less popular among higher education institutions than Facebook and Instagram; however, some Ukrainian universities use it, particularly for international communication. On this platform, institutions interact with their audience through:

- breaking news: X allows for rapid dissemination of brief news and announcements, which is convenient for event announcements, schedule changes, or other important messages;

- professional communication: institutions use X for participating in professional discussions, exchanging opinions with colleagues and researchers from other countries;

- hashtags: use of hashtags enhances the posts visibility and attracts a broader audience. For example, hashtags like #Science, #Education, and #Ukraine help effectively locate relevant content.

However, as the results of this study indicate, the X platform is not popular among higher education institutions in Kharkiv as a communication channel.

LinkedIn is a platform for professional communication. Some HEIs create official pages on LinkedIn to interact with the professional community, stakeholders, alumni, and others. On LinkedIn, universities communicate through:

- professional achievements: HEIs use LinkedIn to publish information about academic work, faculty and students' achievements, as well as their collaboration with other universities and organizations;

- career opportunities: universities post job vacancies, internships, and other career opportunities for students and alumni. This helps maintain connections with graduates and attract new students and partners;

- networking: for HEIs, LinkedIn can become an effective tool for establishing professional connections, participation in professional groups and discussions.

TikTok, as one of the most popular social networks among young people, can be an effective tool for higher education institutions. This platform is distinguished by its creative approach to video content, requiring short videos, unlike YouTube, which allows videos of any length. The main types of communication that universities can utilize on this platform include:

- short videos to explain complex topics, concepts, or important facts;

- tips and hacks for effective studying, exam preparation, writing essays, term papers, and graduation projects;

- videos about admission conditions, deadlines, study programs, and opportunities for higher education students;
- short videos for promoting upcoming events, conferences, and open days;
- reviews from higher education students and alumni;
- success stories of the institution, its faculty, and students;
- short videos about research, discoveries, and projects;
- videos of laboratory experiments, research and demonstrations;
- video reports from concerts, exhibitions, and festivals organized by the institution;
- videos about charitable and volunteer projects, social responsibility initiatives;
- video tips and recommendations for students concerning studies, career development, exam preparation, etc.;
- short clips from webinars and workshops on various topics that may be useful for students;
- videos from students about their daily life, studies, and leisure;
- challenges and trends (participating in popular TikTok challenges and trends which engage the audience;
- interactive content: videos where the institution asks questions to its audience, conducts polls, collects feedback; organizing competitions and contests among students, applicants, and followers with prizes and rewards.

Vimeo is a platform for professional video content that can also be beneficial for university branding, but it is not widely popular among HEIs. Universities most commonly choose YouTube, with TikTok being less frequent, video content is also published on Facebook and Instagram. On Vimeo, universities can publish:

- educational content such as lectures, webinars, and video classes;
- informational videos, presentations of educational programs, and event broadcasts;
- interviews and feedback;
- video presentations of scientific events, research, and projects;
- coverage of cultural events, activities, and social initiatives;
- advice for applicants and students from alumni or senior students, including webinars and workshops;
- student work related to video art and animation;
- video blogs from students and faculty;
- students' video projects, etc.

Another platform found among university communication channels is Pinterest, which is a social network that allows creating visual content, organizing it into boards, and engaging audiences through images, infographics, and other visual materials. Universities can use this platform to communicate with their audience by posting: infographics to explain important data, statistics, or processes; visual announcements about events, university news, deadlines, and other important messages; visual explanations of concepts, theories, or examples; advice on studying, with visual materials detailing educational programs, courses, and specializations; visual content about educational programs, departments, and opportunities for students; photos from cultural, social, and sports events involving the university; posters for upcoming events such as concerts, performances, and conferences; infographics with career advice, job search tips, and resume writing; graphic materials with quotes and testimonials from students and alumni; graphic posters demonstrating research results and academic achievements; thematic boards related to specific aspects of university life or particular specializations/educational programs.

As it is well-known, the popularity of the messaging application Telegram has been increasing recently, and more and more HEIs are using it as a communication channel with their

audience: official representations are being created on the platform for disseminating important information to their audience, including prospective students, current students, faculty members, researchers, and all interested parties. It is important to highlight the reasons for the growing popularity of this platform in Ukraine in recent years.

Figure 1 displays statistics on the use of social networks/messengers for communication in 2022–2023 and for receiving news in 2022–2023. As we can see, in both cases, Telegram occupies the top position (despite being a messaging application rather than a social network).

Advertising on Telegram, which specializes in Internet marketing research, Telegram's popularity as a fast and convenient communication tool is on the rise. As shown in Figure 1, Telegram holds leading positions in both 2022 and 2023, with a trend towards increasing the number of users. Such popularity is attributed to its user-friendly interface, the ability to send not only text messages but also large files. It is constantly improving, can function even with a weak Internet connection, etc.

Fig. 1. Statistics on social media usage in 2022–2023 (<http://surl.li/uvodrl>)

Figure 2 demonstrates more detailed information regarding the reasons for Telegram's popularity among other messaging applications. Among the main reasons for Telegram's popularity are convenience, speed, and efficiency. These features attract users who live and work in an environment characterized by extreme dynamism, rapid changes, vast information flows, and the need to solve various tasks – both work and daily related – in a short time. Considering the advantages of this messaging application, almost every higher education institution in Kharkiv uses Telegram as a tool for engaging their audience, for quick and convenient communication, and for timely dissemination of information. They operate not only an official Telegram channel but also channels of faculties, departments, and educational programs aimed at engaging their target audience. Telegram provides the opportunity to create:

- channels designed for disseminating information, which can be used as news lines or blogs;

- chats intended for communication, where all participants can write and send messages;
- bots designed for content delivery; beyond that, bots can interact with external services, collecting information from them and “responding” to user queries.

Fig. 2. Reasons for the growing popularity of Telegram among Ukrainians (<http://surl.li/uvodrl>)

As the research results show, all the analyzed official Telegram representations of state-owned higher education institutions in Kharkiv, listed on their official websites, are the channels created with the ability for users to leave comments (mostly in cases when the channel is specifically oriented towards prospective students). However, some of the channels do not permit comments (when the channel functions as a news line).

When working with Telegram channels, the presentation of information is crucial, i.e. the content must be structured: the text should be divided into paragraphs, sentences should be concise, and the use of hashtags will help organize and later locate the content easily. Additionally, the use of emojis in texts should not be neglected, as they make the content more visual, appealing, and emotional. This is particularly important when working with young people, who are the primary target audience of higher education Telegram channels and tends to better perceive visualized information.

Some higher education institutions, in addition to channels, create Telegram bots that allow users to receive various consultations, calculations, news, answers to questions, etc. For example, Simon Kuznets Kharkiv National Economic University after has several external testing (EIT) bots designed to assist prospective students in preparing for exams in various subjects, and they also offer prize draws for academic achievements. Figure 3 displays a list of Telegram bots, and Figure 4, 5 provides an example of the “EIT Mathematics” bot interface. Consequently, chatbots enable the automation of certain processes and provide users with necessary information promptly.

As previously mentioned, HEIs predominantly utilize Telegram channels. This study analyzed all the links to official Telegram channels listed on the official websites of these institutions as one of their communication channels. Additionally, information was collected

concerning the number of subscribers for each analyzed Telegram channel of the institutions as of June 30, 2024. The relevant information is presented in Table 2.

Table 2

List of telegram channels of institutions of higher education of the III-IV levels of accreditation of the state-owned form of ownership in the city of Kharkiv²

Name of the institution of higher education	Link to the official Telegram page	Number of followers
State Biotechnological University	—	—
National Aerospace University «Kharkiv Aviation Institute»	https://t.me/aerospaceuniversity	1,916
National Technical University «Kharkiv Polytechnic Institute»	https://t.me/s/NTU_KhPI_press	1,990
National University of Civil Defence of Ukraine	https://t.me/nuczu_vstup	222
National University of Pharmacy	—	—
Yaroslav Mudryi National Law University	https://t.me/NLU1804official	6,605
Ukrainian Engineering and Pedagogical Academy	https://t.me/uepakharkiv	336
Ukrainian state university of railway transport	https://t.me/UkrDuzt_of	514
Kharkiv State Academy of Design and fine Arts	—	—
Kharkiv State Academy of Physical Culture	https://t.me/hdakovstup2023	421
Kharkiv State Academy of Physical Culture	—	—
Kharkiv National Automobile and Highway University	https://t.me/khnahu/	870
Simon Kuznets Kharkov National University of Economics	https://t.me/abitura_2019	2,445

² Data collected by the authors, as of June 30, 2024, taken from the official websites of higher education institutions

Kharkiv National Medical University	https://t.me/KhNMUof	978
Kharkiv National University of Internal Affairs	https://t.me/khnuia	2,092
V. N. Karazin Kharkiv National University	https://t.me/karazinuniver1804	7,134
H.S. Skovoroda Kharkiv National Pedagogical University	https://t.me/Skovoroda_university	2,223
Kharkiv National University of Arts named after I. P. Kotlyarevsky	—	—
O.M. Beketov National University of Urban Economy in Kharkiv	https://t.me/beketovuni_vstup	1,802
Kharkiv National University of Radio Electronics	https://t.me/nure_osvita	1,219

According to the content analysis of official websites of state-owned higher education institutions (HEIs) of III-IV accreditation levels in Kharkiv, they prefer using Telegram – the most popular and convenient messenger among the available and accessible messengers for communication with the target audience. As Table 2 shows, 15 out of 20 HEIs have their official Telegram channels, which constitutes 75% of the total number of institutions surveyed.

Fig. 3. Examples of Telegram bots offered by the Simon Kuznets Kharkiv National University of Economics

Table 3

Rating of telegram channels of institutions of higher education III-IV levels of accreditation of the state-owned form of Kharkiv (by the number of followers)³

Name of the institution of higher education	Link to the official Telegram page /	Number of followers
V. N. Karazin Kharkiv National University	https://t.me/karazinuniver1804	7134
Yaroslav Mudryi National Law University	https://t.me/NLU1804official	6605
Simon Kuznets Kharkov National University of Economics	https://t.me/abitura_2019	2445
H.S. Skovoroda Kharkiv National Pedagogical University	https://t.me/Skovoroda_university	2223
Kharkiv National University of Internal Affairs	https://t.me/khnuia	2092
National Technical University «Kharkiv Polytechnic Institute»	https://t.me/s/NTU_KhPI_press	1990
National Aerospace University «Kharkiv Aviation Institute»	https://t.me/aerospaceuniversity	1916
O. M. Beketov National University of Urban Economy in Kharkiv	https://t.me/beketovuni_vstup	1802
Kharkiv National University of Radio Electronics	https://t.me/nure_osvita	1219
Kharkiv National Medical University	https://t.me/KhNMUof	978
Kharkiv National Automobile and Highway University	https://t.me/khnahu/	870
Ukrainian state university of railway transport	https://t.me/UkrDuzt_of	514
Kharkiv State Academy of Culture	https://t.me/hdakvstup2023	421
Ukrainian Engineering and Pedagogical Academy	https://t.me/uepakharkiv	336
National University of Civil Defense of Ukraine	https://t.me/nuczu_vstup	222
State Biotechnological University	—	—
National University of Pharmacy	—	—
Kharkiv State Academy of Design and fine Arts	—	—
Kharkiv State Academy of Physical Culture	—	—
Kharkiv National University of Arts named after I. P. Kotlyarevsky	—	—

³ Дані станом на 30.06.2024

Fig. 6. Ranking of Telegram channels of State Higher Education Institutions of III-IV accreditation levels in Kharkiv (by number of subscribers)

According to the data obtained, the largest number of subscribers is held by V. N. Karazin Kharkiv National University with 7,134 subscribers and Yaroslav Mudryi National Law University with 6,605 subscribers. The Telegram channels of Kharkiv National Economic University named after Simon Kuznets, Kharkiv National University of Internal Affairs, and H. S. Skovoroda Kharkiv National Pedagogical University have between 2,000 and 3,000 subscribers. The channels of M. E. Zhukovsky National Aerospace University “Kharkiv Aviation Institute”, National Technical University “Kharkiv Polytechnic Institute”, O. M. Beketov Kharkiv National University of Municipal Economy, and Kharkiv National University of Radio Electronics have up to 2,000 subscribers. This states that there is potential to gain a larger number of subscribers with an active communication strategy, notwithstanding the type of student contingent at HEIs.

During this study, information was collected and structured regarding the number of web representations of HEIs, which indicates the level of their incorporation into the modern web space. Table 4 presents data concerning the availability of official web presences of HEIs on various platforms.

Table 4

Data on the availability of higher education institutions with an official web presence on one or another platform⁴

Name of the institution of higher education	Facebook	Instagram	YouTube	X (Twitter)	LinkedIn	TikTok	Vimeo	Pinterest	Telegram
State Biotechnological University	+	+	+						
National Aerospace University «Kharkiv Aviation Institute»	+	+	+						+

⁴ The data were collected by the authors from the official telegram channels of higher education institutions, as of June 30, 2024.

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National Technical University «Kharkiv Polytechnic Institute»	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
National University of Civil Defence of Ukraine	+	+	+	+			+
National University of Pharmacy	+	+	+			+	
Yaroslav Mudryi National Law University	+	+	+	+	+		+
Ukrainian Engineering and Pedagogical Academy	+	+	+				+
Ukrainian state university of railway transport	+	+	+				+
Kharkiv State Academy of Design and fine Arts	+	+	+				
Kharkiv State Academy of Culture	+	+	+				+
Kharkiv State Academy of Physical Culture	+	+	+				
Kharkiv National Automobile and Highway University	+	+	+				+
Simon Kuznets Kharkov National University of Economics	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Kharkiv National Medical University	+	+	+	+	+		+
Kharkiv National University of Internal Affairs	+	+	+	+			+
V. N. Karazin Kharkiv National University	+	+	+			+	+
H.S. Skovoroda Kharkiv National Pedagogical University	+	+	+				+
Kharkiv National University of Arts named after I. P. Kotlyarevsky	+		+				
O.M. Beketov National University of Urban Economy in Kharkiv	+	+	+				+
Kharkiv National University of Radio Electronics	+	+	+	+	+		+

Based on the data in Table 4, it is possible to state that among digital communication tools, Kharkiv HEIs prefer the four most popular among Ukrainians, platforms: Facebook, YouTube, Instagram, and Telegram. HEIs actively use these platforms to attract prospective students, highlight the conditions and rules of the admission campaign, provide consultations and communicate with applicants (and/or their parents), inform and showcase various aspects of HEI life, announce events, and communicate with students, faculty, staff, and other interested parties. In contrast, the use of LinkedIn by HEIs is primarily focused on establishing business connections with alumni, stakeholders, partners, and researchers. Such platforms as X, Vimeo, and Pinterest

are not particularly popular as communication channels, neither among the HEIs (information has not been updated for several years) nor among users. For example, the official page of the National Technical University “Kharkiv Polytechnic Institute” on Vimeo (<https://vimeo.com/presskhpi>) (see Figure 7) shows that the last post was dated 2017 and the number of subscribers is 15. Therefore, it is possible to make a conclusion that this channel of interaction with the audience is not currently relevant.

Fig. 7. Data from the official vimeo page of the National Technical University "Kharkiv Polytechnic Institute" as of 01.07.2024

Based on the data in Table 4, the authors developed a ranking of social networks used by higher education institutions of III-IV accreditation levels in Kharkiv, as presented in Table 5.

Table 5

Rating of social networks used by higher education institutions of the III-IV levels of accreditation of the state-owned form of Kharkiv⁵

Place in the rating	The name of the social network/messenger	The number of institutions of higher education	Amount in percent
1	Facebook	20	100%
1	YouTube	20	100%
2	Instagram	19	95%
3	Telegram	15	75%
4	X	7	35%
5	LinkedIn	5	25%
6	TikTok	3	15%
7	Vimeo	1	5%
7	Pinterest	1	5%

The ranking is based on the quantitative measure of how many Kharkiv HEIs have a web representation on each social network/messenger. According to these indicators, Facebook and YouTube take the first place, with 100% of the analyzed HEIs having official presences; Instagram holds the second place with 95% of the analyzed HEIs having official presences; Telegram is in the third place, with 75% of the analyzed HEIs having official presences; the fourth, fifth, and sixth places are taken by X, LinkedIn, and TikTok, with 35%, 25%, and 15% of the analyzed HEIs

⁵ Data collected by the authors, as of July 1, 2024

having official representations respectively. Each university has one representation in Vimeo and Pinterest, accounting for 5% each, which corresponds to one HEI, placing them in the final seventh position. It is also important to note that these presences have not been updated with current information for a long time.

Based on the data presented in Table 5, the authors created a visualization of the ranking of platforms used by higher education institutions to position themselves in the online space (see Figure 8).

Fig. 8. Popularity of platforms among state higher education institutions of III–IV accreditation levels in Kharkiv

Figure 8 shows social networks (messengers) ranked by popularity among HEIs of III-IV accreditation levels in Kharkiv. The research indicates that Facebook and YouTube are the most popular social networks, with 100% of HEIs using them; thus, all 20 HEIs have official representations on these platforms. Instagram follows in the second place, used by 95% of HEIs, while Telegram ranks third with 75%.

The popularity of these social networks (messengers) is attributed to their versatility. Facebook and Instagram, while being primarily social networks, also offer their own messengers, facilitating both content publication and direct communication with the interested users. Telegram, being inherently a messenger, provides tools for convenient and efficient content publishing and dissemination. Additionally, these platforms provide an opportunity to distribute various content formats, including texts, images, videos, and animations, which explains the lesser focus of HEIs on other platforms specializing in specific content formats, such as video (TikTok) or text (X).

The popularity of YouTube is conditioned by the fact that video content is inherently popular among users. Some higher education institutions also use TikTok to distribute video content, but as the research shows, only 20% of HEIs are engaged in this, and not all of them have a significant number of subscribers or content. However, such institutions as Kharkiv Semen Kuznets National Economic University and Kharkiv V. N. Karazin National University actively maintain this communication channel, with 2,492 and 8,550 subscribers respectively, as illustrated in Figure 9.

Fig. 9. Data from official TikTok pages of V.N. Karazin Kharkiv National University and Simon Kuznets Kharkiv National University of Economics

The data collected, analyzed, and described in this study allowed the authors to compile a summary statistic on the number of subscribers for each HEI on the most popular platforms (see Figure 8) as of June 30, 2024. This statistic, showing which HEIs use these platforms as official communication channels with their target audience, is presented in Table 6.

Table 6

Generalized statistics on the number of subscribers on the most popular platforms among Kharkiv institutions of higher education⁶

Name of the institution of higher education	Number of followers			
	Facebook	Instagram	YouTube	Telegram
State Biotechnological University (DBU)	1500	1161	8	—
National Aerospace University «Kharkiv Aviation Institute» (M. E. Zhukovsky NAU "KHAI")	3200	8699	18500	1916
National Technical University «Kharkiv Polytechnic Institute» (NTU "KhPI")	7600	6916	634	1990
National University of Civil Defense of Ukraine (NUCSU)	2300	1621	2400	222
National University of Pharmacy (NPAU)	6900	3007	1008	—
Yaroslav Mudryi National Law University (NYU named after Yaroslav the Wise)	16000	15400	7570	6605
Ukrainian Engineering and Pedagogical Academy (UEPA)	3300	1605	2310	336
Ukrainian state university of railway transport (UEPA)	1500	3417	789	514
Kharkiv State Academy of Design and Arts (KHADM)	1300	1588	217	—
Kharkiv State Academy of Culture (KhSAC)	551	750	163	421
Kharkiv State Academy of Physical Culture (KSAPC)	1600	1985	588	—
Kharkiv National Automobile and Highway University (KNAHU)	1900	1504	327	870
Simon Kuznets Kharkiv National University of Economics (KhNU of Economics)	3800	8238	2810	2464
Kharkiv National Medical University (KNMU)	7000	4738	1730	978
Kharkiv National University of Internal Affairs (KNUIA)	12000	13700	6860	2092

⁶ The data were collected by the authors as of June 30, 2024

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V. N. Karazin Kharkiv National University (KhNU)	29000	22500	5001	7134
H.S. Skovoroda Kharkiv National Pedagogical University (KNPU)	6500	3532	1006	2223
Kharkiv National University of Arts named after I. P. Kotlyarevsky (KNUA)	2700	—	1009	—
O.M. Beketov National University of Urban Economy in Kharkiv (KNUUE)	3400	3001	168	1802
Kharkiv National University of Radio Electronics (KNURE)	3200	14400	5800	1219

The data collected and displayed in Table 6 are visualized in Figure 10, which illustrates the popularity of each platform based on the number of subscribers for each individual HEI and provides an opportunity to compare their subscriber counts.

Figure 10 illustrates the results of a comparative analysis of the number of subscribers on the most popular platforms among HEIs of III-IV levels of accreditation in the city of Kharkiv (Facebook, Instagram, YouTube, Telegram). Each institution is represented separately on the diagram, with the number of subscribers indicated for each platform. This allows for an examination of which platform has the highest number of subscribers within each individual HEI as well as across all analyzed HEIs.

Let's review the statistics from the diagram in Figure 10 for each platform:

Facebook:

the largest number of subscribers is observed for Kharkiv V. N. Karazin National University (29,000 subscribers).

high figures are also seen for Yaroslav the Wise National University of Law (16,000 subscribers) and the National Technical University “Kharkiv Polytechnic Institute” (12,000 subscribers).

Instagram:

Kharkiv V. N. Karazin National University also leads in the number of subscribers on Instagram (22,500 subscribers).

Yaroslav the Wise National University of Law has 15,400 subscribers, Kharkiv National University of Radio Electronics has 14,400 subscribers, and Kharkiv National University of Internal Affairs has 13,700 subscribers.

Fig. 10. Comparison of number of subscribers on Web platforms most popular among state higher education institutions of III–IV accreditation levels in Kharkiv

YouTube:

the number of subscribers on YouTube is somewhat lower across all higher education institutions compared to other platforms; however, M. E. Zhukovsky National Aerospace University “Kharkiv Aviation Institute” has the largest number of subscribers (18,500 subscribers).

other notable figures include Yaroslav the Wise National University of Law (7,570 subscribers), Kharkiv National University of Internal Affairs (6,860 subscribers), and Kharkiv V. N. Karazin National University with 5,001 subscribers, as well as Kharkiv National University of Radio Electronics with 5,800 subscribers.

Telegram:

the largest number of subscribers is found at Kharkiv V. N. Karazin National University (7,134 subscribers).

other notable figures include Yaroslav the Wise National University of Law (6,605 subscribers), Kharkiv Semen Kuznets National Economic University named after (2,464 subscribers), Kharkiv H. S. Skovoroda National Pedagogical University (2,223 subscribers), and Kharkiv National University of Internal Affairs (2,092 subscribers).

Based on the data presented in Figure 10, it is possible to draw the following conclusions:

- Facebook and Instagram are the most popular platforms among higher education institutions in Kharkiv in terms of the number of subscribers.

- Kharkiv V. N. Karazin National University has the highest number of subscribers across three out of four platforms: Facebook, Instagram, and Telegram that may indicate a high level of

activity and effective communication strategies provided by the university on these social networks/messengers.

- Telegram channels of Kharkiv higher education institutions are also popular, although the number of subscribers is somewhat lower compared to other platforms. Nevertheless, they should be actively involved in the branding process.

- YouTube channels have fewer subscribers compared to other platforms, which may indicate less activity and interest in this format among the students. An exception is the YouTube channel of M.E. Zhukovsky National Aerospace University “Kharkiv Aviation Institute”, which, as of June 30, 2024, has 18,500 subscribers, reflecting a strong promotion strategy of the institution for this communication channel among potential users.

The obtained data indicate that higher education institutions with fewer subscribers should more actively use social networks/messengers to enhance their integration into the global communication space, attract new subscribers, and develop an effective brand.

Conclusions

Therefore, the study involved a content analysis of the official websites of 20 higher education institutions of III-IV accreditation levels with state ownership in Kharkiv, aimed at identifying effective online representations. Based on the collected information, a ranking of social networks/messengers for these HEIs was established. This ranking was formulated based on the number of HEIs among the selected ones, which have a presence on each platform. The research enabled the identification of the most popular social networks/messengers among the target audience of HEIs of III-IV accreditation levels with state ownership in Kharkiv, namely: Facebook (100% of HEIs), YouTube (100% of HEIs), Instagram (95% of HEIs), and Telegram (75% of HEIs).

Assessment of each platform popularity, analysis of its advantages and communication capabilities allows for specifying the following observations:

Facebook is the most popular platform among HEIs of III-IV accreditation levels with state ownership in Kharkiv. It is highly effective for disseminating news, engaging the audience, and facilitating further interaction.

YouTube is widely used by HEIs to create long-lasting video content and to highlight events, activities, publish educational, informational, promotional, and cultural content. It is highly effective for providing a HEI's “showcase”, sharing educational content, recording lectures, presenting scientific research, promoting events and information about the institution.

Instagram is a platform popular among youth, offering high effectiveness for visual presentation, increasing audience engagement, and promoting events, advertising materials, and reporting the HEI's life through photos and short videos with brief textual descriptions. The use of hashtags is effective for better content promotion and attracting more followers.

Telegram is a messenger that is becoming increasingly popular among Ukrainians in general and HEIs specifically, due to its speed and convenience for information distribution. It is highly effective for prompt communication, informing, sending news updates, announcing events, supporting communities, and providing feedback from students, prospective students, stakeholders, etc.

The next stage of the study involved analysis of the web representatives regarding the information relevance and the number of followers. Based on the statistics concerning the number of followers, a ranking of Telegram channels for HEIs, which are rapidly gaining popularity, was created. The largest Telegram channels are those of Kharkiv V.N. Karazin National University with 7,134 followers and Yaroslav the Wise National Law University with 6,605 followers.

Additionally, a comparison was conducted of the number of followers for the official web representations of HEIs across the four most popular platforms identified in this study (Facebook, YouTube, Instagram, Telegram). This comparison allowed to determine which platform is the most popular for each HEI, and provided practical recommendations for enhancing the effectiveness of HEI presence in the modern web space.

Based on the results of the study, conceptual principles for improving the effectiveness of HEI branding campaigns through mediatization – effective communication activities on social networks/messengers – are developed:

diversification of network communication channels gives a synergistic effect in covering the target audience of information consumers;

regular content updating and engagement in interactive dialogue with the audience contribute to a significant increase in the number of followers on all web platforms;

systematic use of analytics to track the effectiveness of communication strategies and content adaptation according to followers' interests is a crucial tool for enhancing the quality of HEI communication and marketing efforts;

engaging SMM (Social Media Marketing) specialists for improving the quality of maintaining accounts in social networks/messengers directly correlates with an increase in the number of followers;

the most effective communication strategy for HEIs is involving followers in creative co-creation and interaction for the promotion of educational services through network media.

The experience of leading HEIs in Kharkiv indicates that the library, as the most qualified communication intermediary, possesses significant potential to enhance the effectiveness of media engagement and brand management. Future research should focus on studying the state of media engagement in libraries at prominent HEIs in the central and western regions of the country to identify the most successful cases and disseminate best practices.

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Медіатизація як базова комунікаційна стратегія університетських бібліотек Харкова

Мета. Метою дослідження є розробка концептуальних засад медіатизації як найбільш ефективної комунікаційної стратегії університетських бібліотек. Унікальний досвід аналітичних та маркетингових практик наукових бібліотек університетів дозволяє їм ефективно відстежувати вплив своїх офіційних акаунтів у соціальних мережах та платформах обміну повідомленнями, тим самим сприяючи формуванню свого унікального іміджу. **Методика.** Використано методи спостереження, порівняння, інтернет-маркетингу, контент-аналізу офіційних сайтів університетів, посилань на офіційні вебпредставництва в соціальних мережах (месенджерах), статистичні та математичні методи, а також системний і соціально-комунікативний підходи. **Результати.** Дослідження дозволило з'ясувати ступінь інтегрованості харківських університетів у глобальний комунікаційний простір через активність їхньої вебприсутності в різних соціальних мережах / месенджерах. Розроблено рейтинги популярності соціальних мереж / месенджерів (Facebook, YouTube, Instagram, Telegram) серед харківських університетів, а також їхніх Telegram-каналів за кількістю підписників. **Висновки.** Університетські бібліотеки володіють потужним аналітичним потенціалом для підвищення ефективності брендингових кампаній університетів через медіатизацію – ефективну комунікаційну діяльність у соціальних мережах / месенджерах. Систематичне використання інструментів вебаналітики для моніторингу ефективності комунікаційних стратегій та адаптації контенту відповідно до інтересів підписників може підвищити якість комунікаційної та маркетингової діяльності закладів вищої освіти.

Ключові слова: університетські бібліотеки Харкова; медіатизація; соціальні мережі; месенджери; інтернет-маркетинг; брендинг

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